

Evaluation of the Causes and Impact of Stress in the Management of Secondary Schools in Oshimili North and South Local Government Areas of Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The main objective was to examine the causes and effects of stress in management of secondary schools in Oshimili North and South L.G.A. Delta State. This study adopted descriptive survey design. With the help of research assistants, a total of 551 (93.71%) questionnaire were fully completed and returned which was utilized for the study. Analysis was done using mean and standard deviation with the aid of four likert scale to generate the data for the analysis and t-test to test for the hypotheses. Findings shown that causes of stress are work load at work, pressure at home, lack of social support, never getting paid overtime, salary that isn't paid on a regular basis, constantly answering questions in the office, working past regular business hours, partner death, divorce, jail time, marriage, losing your job, retirement, reconciliation with your partner, issues with your in-laws, arguments with your partner, changes in your financial situation, pregnancy, health changes, personal injury, friend death, and partner separation. Also findings revealed that impact of stress are hopelessness, poor concentration, worry, restlessness, anger, rashes, overwhelm, isolation, pessimism, emotional outbursts, alcohol, drug abuse, tension, exhaustion, irritability, constipation, forgetfulness, sleep difficulties, aggression, confusion, headache, depression, loss of appetite, backache, fast breathing, ulcer, backache, internal heat, and infertility are all consequences of stress in the study area. The hypotheses was accepted as, according to the t-test result the computed t-value was less (p) at 0.05 and 549 degrees of freedom. It is recommended that to prevent job overload, the government should make sure that schools have an adequate number of teachers. A comfortable atmosphere and a well-equipped classroom will support efficient teaching and learning, and the various stakeholders should guarantee that there are sufficient school facilities to enable instructors to carry out their responsibilities without stress. Also to improve positive interpersonal relationships, *team-building and conflict-resolution seminars and workshops ought to be organized.*

Keywords: Causes, Impact, Management, School, Stress

Introduction

Stress is progressively becoming a part of our daily lives. The Latin word stress has been in common language since the seventeenth century. According to Charles (2021), stress was used to address hardship, adversity, or affliction and stress is best described as a situation where environmental demands exceed the capacity for effective response by the individual. There is no doubt that this days academic work environment is passing through a tremendous change, looking into the nature of work been done and effort put in for promotion by academic staff. No wonder, Obidiegwu (2020) posited that the landscape of the education is continuously changing due to the changes impose by the environment. These changes have introduced more work load on the workers as a result heading to the increases of the stress in the environment. Academic challenges that render the teachers more vulnerable to stress and anxiety is particularly due to particular nature of their work; teaching, researching, managing the students and adapting to the changing world. Stress is a matter of personal perception. Teachers' stress is a specific type of occupational stress. Teaching has been viewed as a stressful occupation, and this has been recognized as a widespread problem in the educational sector (Gustem-Carnicer et al, 2019). In addition to academic requirements related with family members, faculty members, personal desires, and even time management, more strain is caused by social adjustment for newly employed teachers, particularly adjusting to life and managing family and friends. Teachers stress has been identified as the teachers experience from unpleasant negative emotions which includes anger, depression and physiological changes such as rise in heart rate. This occurs as a result of some features of the instructors employment that constitute a threat to his or her self

worth or well-being. Because of this, Khandelwa & Chanber (2020) classified teachers' stress as being caused by certain aspects of their profession as educators and characterized by unpleasant negative feelings like irritation, despair, worry, and anxiousness. There are various types of stress, according to Amalu & Achi (2020). Episodic Acute Stress: This type of stress is characterized by chaos, out of control, and a constant sense of being in multiple stressful situations; people in this situation are always rushing, frequently late, taking on too many projects, and managing too many demands. It is a fact that people who are prone to episodic acute stress may find their lifestyles so habitual that they resist changing them until they experience severe physical symptoms. The second kind of stress is chronic stress, which is extremely harmful. It is a form of stress that lasts for an apparently endless amount of time and involves constant demands and pressure. People who experience chronic stress are worn out over an extended period of time. A breakdown or even death may result from it since it affects the person's emotional and physical well-being. The third type of stress reaction is called traumatic stress, and it can be brought on by a natural disaster, sexual assault, a potentially fatal accident, or involvement in an activity. Many people who have experienced trauma start to heal gradually after the initial shock and emotional aftermath. But for some people, that will be the start of the trauma-induced psychological and physical symptoms. And nightmares or flashbacks are typical signs of this kind of stress. However, encouragement is the answer to this problem. Lastly, the most prevalent and identifiable type of stress is acute stress. With this kind of stress, the person is aware of the precise cause of their anxiety. For instance, the principal will become stressed when he invites a staff member who is careless in his duties. However, because to the short-term

consequences, the human body relaxes when these stressful situations stop and life returns to normal. By identifying the particular stresses in a person's life and taking constructive steps to lessen their impact, stress management is a collection of strategies, programs, and treatments that assist people deal with stress in their lives. Teachers will advance if they can effectively control their stress. (Amalu & Achi, 2020). According to Copper (2002), stress has been shown to impair effectiveness at work and can result in low performance and productivity, particularly among teachers, as well as job dissatisfaction, low motivation, absenteeism, and turnover. Teachers are frequently under a lot of stress, according to Reglin & Reitzammer (2018). There is no benefit to claiming that stress may have contributed to the poor job performance in secondary schools. This Scholar Brotobor (2021), to propose that a stressful circumstance may have long-term detrimental effects on a person's psychological life, physical health, and mental health. Therefore, the problem statement asks: What are the causes and impacts of stress among teachers in Delta State's public secondary schools in Oshimili North and South LGA? Therefore the purpose of the study is to evaluate the causes and impact of stress in the management of secondary schools in Oshimili North and South local government areas of Delta state, Nigeria. This study remains significant as it examines the causes and impacts of stress in management of secondary schools in Oshimili North and South L.G.A. Delta State. To this regard when the administrators read this work, it will expose the danger of stress on their employees and subordinate. It will also benefit the students, helping them to understand the effect and danger of stress to health. When the curriculum planners read it they will review the business education curriculum to avoid the danger of stress. Findings from this study will be of benefit to scholars

and researchers in business education and educational administration by contributing to the pool of knowledge and literature on causes and impacts of stress in secondary school.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the causes of stress in management of secondary schools in study area?
2. What are the impacts of stress in management of secondary schools in study area?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been generated for the purpose of the study;

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between principals and teachers in their mean ratings on extent of causes of stress in the administration of secondary schools.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between principals and teachers in their mean ratings on extent of impacts of stress in the administration of secondary schools.

Materials and Methods

This study adopted descriptive survey design. The targeted population of this study comprises of 588, that is, 28 principals and 560 teachers in 28 Public Secondary schools in Oshimili North (15 schools) and South (13 schools) Local Government Area of Delta State. Since the population is manageable as there was no sampling. With the help of research assistants, a total of 551 (93.71%) questionnaire were fully completed and returned which was utilized for the study. Data was collected with the aid of well-designed questionnaire which was structured on 4 points Likert type scale of responses. Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD),

Disagree (D). In decision rule, any item with a mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as Agree, while any item below 2.5 is regarded as Disagree. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What are the causes of stress in management of secondary schools in the study area?

This was achieved using mean and standard deviation with the aid of four likert scale to generate the data for the analysis on the causes of stress in management of secondary schools. The parameters in Table 1 revealed that respondents agreed that work load at work with a mean (**X**) of 3.35 and (**SD**) of 0.84, pressure at home with a mean (**X**) of 3.37 and (**SD**) of 0.88, lack of social support with a mean (**X**) of 3.31 and (**SD**) of 0.79, never getting paid overtime with a mean (**X**) of 3.32 and (**SD**) of 0.84, salary that isn't paid on a regular basis with a mean (**X**) of 3.46 and (**SD**) of 0.71, constantly answering questions in the office with a mean (**X**) of 3.37 and (**SD**) of 0.88, working past regular business hours with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.78, partner death with a mean (**X**) of 3.32 and (**SD**) of 0.80, divorce with a mean (**X**) of 3.35 and (**SD**) of 0.84, jail time with a mean (**X**) of 3.25 and (**SD**) of 0.85, marriage with a mean (**X**) of 3.38 and (**SD**) of 0.91, losing your job with a mean (**X**) of 3.44 and (**SD**) of 0.78, retirement with a mean (**X**) of 3.08 and (**SD**) of 0.72, reconciliation with your partner with a mean (**X**) of 2.77 and (**SD**) of 0.82, issues with your in-laws with a mean (**X**) of 3.28 and (**SD**) of 0.70, arguments with your partner with a mean (**X**) of 3.38 and (**SD**) of 0.81, changes in your

financial situation with a mean (**X**) of 3.32 and (**SD**) of 0.80, pregnancy with a mean (**X**) of 3.20 and (**SD**) of 0.76, health changes with a mean (**X**) of 3.18 and (**SD**) of 0.74, personal injury with a mean (**X**) of 3.33 and (**SD**) of 0.86, friend death with a mean (**X**) of 3.31 and (**SD**) of 0.80, and partner separation with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.78. The overall weighted average mean (**X**) of 3.15 and (**SD**) of 0.77 clearly revealed that are all consequences of stress as agreed by respondents. This was collaborated by Amalu and Achi (2020) that causes of stress are denied or delayed promotion, role conflict, role ambiguity, school leadership, school climate, lack of discipline, school management practices, lack of recognition, interpersonal and intergroup conflict, lack of group cohesiveness, work load, work under load, time management, divorce, jail sentence, loss of job, and so on.

TABLE 1: Causes of stress in administration of secondary schools

S/N	Causes of stress	SA	A	SD	D	(X)	(SD)	Decision
1.	Work load at home	223 40.5%	318 57.7%	6 1.08%	4 0.72%	3.37	0.88	Agreed
2.	Work load at work place	225 40.8%	307 55.7%	11 1.99%	8 1.50%	3.35	0.84	Agreed
3.	Pressure at work	216 39.2%	322 58.4%	7 1.27%	6 1.09%	3.39	0.83	Agreed
4.	Low social support	211 41.3%	314 56.9%	15 2.7%	11 1.99%	3.31	0.79	Agreed

5.	Never receive overtime payment	205 37.20%	338 61.34%	5 1.0%	3 0.5%	3.32	0.84	Agreed
6.	Salary is not paid regularly	212 38.5%	289 52.5%	33 5.98%	17 3.08%	3.46	0.71	Agreed
7.	Always answering query in the office	229 41.6%	308 55.9%	8 1.45%	6 1.08%	3.37	0.88	Agreed
8.	Work beyond normal working hours	205 37.2%	320 58.1%	14 2.5%	12 2.2%	3.30	0.78	Agreed
9.	Death of a partner	207 37.6%	322 58.4%	12 2.2%	10 1.8%	3.32	0.80	Agreed
10.	Divorce	237 43.0%	284 51.5%	16 3.0%	14 2.5%	3.35	0.84	Agreed
11.	Jail sentence	221 40.1%	312 56.6%	10 1.8%	8 1.5%	3.25	0.85	Agreed
12.	Marriage	225 40.8%	316 57.4%	6 1.08%	4 0.72%	3.38	0.91	Agreed
13.	Loss of job	211 38.3%	310 56.3%	16 2.9%	14 2.5%	3.44	0.78	Agreed
14.	Retirement	210	303	20	18	3.08	0.72	Agreed

		38.1%	55.0%	3.6%	3.3%			
15.	Reconciliation with a partner	203 36.8%	312 56.6%	19 3.5%	18 3.3%	2.77	0.82	Agreed
16.	Trouble with in-laws	194 35.2%	329 59.7%	15 2.7%	13 2.4%	3.28	0.70	Agreed
17.	Argument with partner	231 41.9%	304 55.2%	9 1.6%	7 1.3%	3.38	0.81	Agreed
18.	Change in your financial status	209 37.9%	318 57.7%	13 2.4%	11 2.0%	3.32	0.80	Agreed
19.	Pregnancy	199 36.1%	310 56.3%	22 4.0%	20 3.6%	3.20	0.76	Agreed
20.	Change in your health	173 31.4%	328 59.5%	26 4.7%	24 4.4%	3.18	0.74	Agreed
21.	Personal injury	212 38.5%	313 56.8%	14 2.5%	12 2.2%	3.33	0.86	Agreed
22.	Death of a friend	223 40.5%	294 53.4%	18 3.3%	16 2.9%	3.31	0.80	Agreed
23.	Separation of a partner	212 38.5%	307 55.7%	17 3.1%	15 2.7%	3.30	0.78	Agreed
	Weighted Average					3.15	0.77	Agreed

	Mean						
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Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D).

Research question 2: What are the effects of stress in administration of secondary schools?

This was achieved using mean and standard deviation with the aid of four likert scale to generate the data for the analysis on the causes of stress in management of secondary schools. The parameters in Table 1 revealed that respondents agreed that hopelessness with a mean (**X**) of and (**SD**) of, poor concentration with a mean (**X**) of 3.23 and (**SD**) of 0.68, worry with a mean (**X**) of 3.34 and (**SD**) of 0.84, restlessness with a mean (**X**) of 3.35 and (**SD**) of 0.84, anger with a mean (**X**) of 3.26 and (**SD**) of 0.71, rashes with a mean (**X**) of 3.31 and (**SD**) of 0.79, overwhelm with a mean (**X**) of 3.38 and (**SD**) of 0.91, isolation with a mean (**X**) of 3.26 and (**SD**) of 0.71, pessimism with a mean (**X**) of 3.35 and (**SD**) of 0.84, emotional outbursts with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.78, alcohol with a mean (**X**) of 3.26 and (**SD**) of 0.71, Sleep difficulties with a mean (**X**) of 3.32 and (**SD**) of 0.70, tension with a mean (**X**) of 3.27 and (**SD**) of 0.72, depression with a mean (**X**) of 3.37 and (**SD**) of 0.88, exhaustion with a mean (**X**) of 3.22 and (**SD**) of 0.72, irritability with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.74, constipation with a mean (**X**) of 3.18 and (**SD**) of 0.71, forgetfulness with a mean (**X**) of 3.34 and (**SD**) of 0.84, confusion with a mean (**X**) of 3.27 and (**SD**) of 0.72, headache with a mean (**X**) of 3.23 and (**SD**) of 0.78, Sweaty palms with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.78, loss of appetite with a mean (**X**) of and (**SD**) of, fast breathing with a mean (**X**) of 3.27 and (**SD**) of 0.72, drug abuse with a mean (**X**) of 3.22 and (**SD**) of 0.73, ulcer with a mean (**X**) of 3.18 and (**SD**) of 0.74, backache with a mean (**X**) of 3.29 and (**SD**) of 0.72, trembling with a mean (**X**) of 3.31 and (**SD**) of 0.77,

aggressiveness with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.78, confusion with a mean (**X**) of 3.26 and (**SD**) of 0.71, internal heat with a mean (**X**) of 3.13 and (**SD**) of 0.72, and infertility with a mean (**X**) of 3.30 and (**SD**) of 0.78. The overall weighted average mean (**X**) of 3.27 and (**SD**) of 0.76 clearly revealed that are all consequences of stress as agreed by respondents. This is in line with this Finney (2013) who pronounced that work - place stress regularly affects 19% to 30% of workers of the all-inclusive work population. Also Emaziye et al, (2023) that unfavourable working condition as a result of work pressure reduced productivity and result to mental health problem in Delta state.

TABLE 2: Impacts of stress in administration of secondary schools

S/N	Effects of Stress	SA	A	SD	D	(X)	(SD)	Decision
1.	Poor concentration	196 35.6%	309 56.1%	25 4.5%	21 3.8%	3.23	0.68	Agreed
2.	Worry	235 42.6%	286 51.9%	16 2.9%	14 2.5%	3.34	0.84	Agreed
3.	Restlessness	231 41.9%	292 53.0%	16 2.9%	12 2.2%	3.35	0.84	Agreed
4.	Hopelessness	219 39.7%	314 57.0%	10 1.8%	8 1.5%	3.35	0.84	Agreed
5.	Anger	225 40.8%	270 49.0%	32 5.8%	24 4.4%	3.26	0.71	Agreed
6.	Rashes	207	322	12	10	3.31	0.79	Agreed

		37.6%	58.4%	2.2%	1.8%			
7.	Overwhelmed	231	304	9 1.6%	7	3.38	0.91	Agreed
		41.9%	55.2%		1.3%			
8.	Loss of appetite	205	315	17	14	3.29	0.72	Agreed
		37.2%	57.2%	3.1%	2.5%			
9.	Isolated	212	289	33	17	3.26	0.71	Agreed
		38.5%	52.5%	5.98%	3.08%			
10.	Pessimistic	221	312	10	8	3.35	0.84	Agreed
		40.1%	56.6%	1.8%	1.5%			
11.	Sleep difficulties	204	292	29	26	3.22	0.70	Agreed
		37.0%	53.0%	5.3%	4.7%			
12.	Emotional outbursts	207	317	15	12	3.30	0.78	Agreed
		37.6%	57.5%	2.7%	2.2%			
13.	Alcohol	198	319	18	16	3.26	0.71	Agreed
		35.9%	57.9%	3.3%	2.9%			
14.	Tensed	220	286	24	21	3.27	0.72	Agreed
		39.9%	51.9%	4.4%	3.8%			
15.	Depressed	233	298	11	9	3.37	0.88	Agreed
		42.3%	54.1%	2.0%	1.6%			
16.	Fatigue	206	288	30	27	3.22	0.72	Agreed

		37.4%	52.3%	5.5%	4.9%			
17.	Irritability	199	310	22	20	3.20	0.74	Agreed
		36.1%	56.3%	4.0%	3.6%			
18.	Constipation	173	328	26	24	3.18	0.71	Agreed
		31.4%	59.5%	4.7%	4.4%			
19.	Headache	185	326	21	19	3.23	0.78	Agreed
		33.6%	59.2%	3.8%	3.5%			
20.	Fast breathing	203	312	19	17	3.27	0.72	Agreed
		36.8%	56.6%	3.5%	3.1%			
21.	Sweaty palms	205	320	14	12	3.30	0.78	Agreed
		37.2%	58.1%	2.5%	2.2%			
22.	Trembling	212	307	17	15	3.31	0.77	Agreed
		38.5%	55.7%	3.1%	2.7%			
23.	Drug abuse	187	321	25	18	3.22	0.73	Agreed
		33.9%	58.3%	4.5%	3.3%			
24.	Ulcer	215	257	41	38	3.18	0.74	Agreed
		39.0%	46.6%	7.4%	7.0%			
25.	Backache	233	268	26	24	3.29	0.72	Agreed
		42.3%	48.6%	4.7%	4.4%			
26.	Forgetfulness	214	305	17	15	3.30	0.78	Agreed

		38.8%	55.4%	3.1%	2.7%			
27.	Aggressiveness	220	292	21	18	3.30	0.78	Agreed
		39.9%	53.0%	3.8%	3.3%			
28.	Confusion	212	294	24	21	3.26	0.71	Agreed
		38.5%	53.4%	4.3%	3.8%			
29.	Internal heat	177	305	35	32	3.13	0.72	Agreed
		32.1%	55.4%	6.4%	5.8%			
30.	Infertility	242	258	27	24	3.30	0.78	Agreed
		43.9%	46.8%	4.9%	4.4%			
	Weighted Average Mean					3.27	0.76	Agreed

Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D).

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were guided at significance level of 0.05

HO₁: There is no significant difference between principals and teachers in their mean rating on the causes of stress in administration of secondary schools in Oshimili North/South LGA of Delta State.

The hypothesis was accepted as, according to the t-test result in Table 4, the computed t-value 1.18 was less (p) at 0.05 and 549 degrees of freedom. According to their mean rating of the stressors in secondary school administration in Oshimili North/South LGA, principals and

teachers do not significantly differ from one another.

Table 4: t-test result in the mean responses between principals and teachers in their mean rating on the causes of stress in administration of secondary schools in Oshimili North/South LGA

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	SL	t.cal	t.crit	Decision
Principals	28	3.28	0.94	549	0.05	1.18	1.96	NS
Teachers	523	3.11	0.97					

HO₂: Principals' and teachers' mean ratings of the impact of stress on secondary school administration in Oshimili North/South LGA of Delta State do not differ significantly.

The hypothesis was accepted when, according to the t-test result in Table 5, the computed t-value 1.16 was less (p) at 0.05 and 549 degrees of freedom. This indicates that there is no discernible difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the impact of stress on secondary school administration in Oshimili North/South LGA.

Table 5: t-test result in the mean responses between principals and teachers in their mean rating on the effects of stress in administration of secondary schools

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	SL	t.cal	t.crit	Decision
Principals	28	3.24	0.92	549	0.05	1.16	1.96	NS
Teachers	523	3.07	0.94					

Conclusion and Recommendations

Findings shown that causes of stress are work load at work, pressure at home, lack of social support, never getting paid overtime, salary that isn't paid on a regular basis, constantly answering questions in the office, working past regular business hours, partner death, divorce, jail time, marriage, losing your job, retirement, reconciliation with your partner, issues with your in-laws, arguments with your partner, changes in your financial situation, pregnancy, health changes, personal injury, friend death, and partner separation. Also findings revealed that impact of stress are hopelessness, poor concentration, worry, restlessness, anger, rashes, overwhelm, isolation, pessimism, emotional outbursts, alcohol, drug abuse, tension, exhaustion, irritability, constipation, forgetfulness, sleep difficulties, aggression, confusion, headache, depression, loss of appetite, backache, fast breathing, ulcer, backache, internal heat, and infertility are all consequences of stress in the study area. The hypotheses was accepted as, according to the t-test result the computed t-value was less (p) at 0.05 and 549 degrees of freedom. It is recommended that to prevent job overload, the government should make sure that schools have an adequate number of teachers. A comfortable atmosphere and a well-equipped classroom will support efficient teaching and learning, and the various stakeholders should guarantee that there are sufficient school facilities to enable instructors to carry out their responsibilities without stress. Also to improve positive interpersonal relationships, team-building and conflict-resolution seminars and workshops ought to be organized.

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Received: 22 July 2025

Revised: 26 July 2025

Accepted: 29 July 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.16782030](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16782030)

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